

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Galician farmers' interest in improving soil quality

Healthy soil is crucial for food production, yet over 60% of EU soils are in poor condition due to farming, pollution, and climate change. The SoildiverAgro project seeks to understand farmers' decisions on sustainable soil management and promote practices that improve soil health, boost crop yields, and benefit the environment. Farmers who believe in sustainable soil practices are more likely to try them, especially if they see support from their community, neighbors, and agricultural groups. Success stories, expert advice, and financial help can give them the confidence to make lasting changes. But overall, it is important to understand how farmers define good soil, how they assess it, and how much they believe their actions can help solve soil problems.

In Galicia, the Atlantic region of Spain, the study focused on crop diversification—growing different species (e.g., potatoes and vegetables) either together or in rotation—to enhance soil

quality. It gathered data from 62 completed questionnaires, with consent, through collaboration with research centers, farmers' associations, local groups, agricultural newspapers, and social media accounts of participating organizations.

Galician farmers were keen on improving soil quality, with a preference for practices such as reducing plowing frequency, incorporating crop residue, using catch crops, and intercropping. They also recognized the benefits of covering fields with organic matter, long crop rotations, and precision fertilization. However, challenges like difficult access to plots were seen as issues not easily addressed through policy or advice. While advice from agricultural machinery suppliers was considered, it didn't strongly influence adoption of new practices. Farmers viewed policy tools, especially subsidies, as crucial for supporting soil improvement efforts.

1. Potato field assay carried out in the SoildiverAgro project.

KEYWORDS

Sustainable soil management, crop diversification, farmer perception, sustainable farming practices, public subsidies

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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